

eBPF - A First Look

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Abstract: BPF is executed in kernel space. BPF can be loaded into the kernel at runtime. BPF can be used to dynamically trace kernel function calls. BPF runs in a sandboxed environment, minimizing the risk of harm to the system.

Keywords: Block, Detect, GitHub, Linux, Lua, Master, Risk, Tool

1. Preface

This paper was written in 2019 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20190508> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

BPF (Berkeley Packet Filter) is nothing new; it has been used in tools such as *tcpdump* for efficient packet tracing for years. In recent kernel versions, especially since version 4.1, a range of new additions have been made to BPF, allowing it to be used for much more than packet filtering. This article intends to give a peek into using BPF and showcase some of BPF's capabilities.

Because of the many additions to BPF it is also referred to as *eBPF*, the 'e' standing for *extended*. For tasks which are handled by the Linux kernel, BPF is more efficient than traditional event tracing methods because it allows for direct instrumentation of any kernel function. Thus BPF can be attached to all kinds of event sources. BPF runs in a *sandboxed kernel environment* which guarantees the program does not cause any harm to the system through its application logic. This makes it well suited as a means to monitor events or debug on production systems. A risk which still remains is an impact on performance if a large number of events is monitored.

An existing collection of tools using BPF can be found in the *bpfcc-tools* package for Debian systems. One useful tool is *opensnoop*, which allows for monitoring the files opened either system wide or for a single program by tracing the *do_sys_open* kernel function.

Another useful BPF program is *tcpretrans*, which traces *tcp retransmits*. Without BPF, a common way to trace tcp retransmits would be using a packetcapture and analyzing the packets by using a tool such as *tcpdump*. With BPF, we can attach a *kprobe* so the *tcp_retransmit_skb* kernel function, which is a more elegant solution. From *tcpretrans*:

```
# initialize BPF
b = BPF(text=bpf_text)
b.attach_kprobe(event="tcp_retransmit_skb",
fn_name="trace_retransmit")
```

The function *trace_retransmit* is a C function defined earlier in the source file. It gathers information on the retransmit and is executed every time a retransmit happens.

3. Using BPF

Writing programs directly using eBPF instructions is time consuming and is comparable to coding in assembly. There are however approachable front ends available with varying levels of abstraction and capabilities. In this article, *bcc* [1] (BPF compiler collection) is used. *Bcc* offers frontends in both Python and Lua. While this first example using the Python interface is very minimalistic, it demonstrates with how little code the *ptrace_attach* system call can be monitored to detect a form of *process injection* [2].

```
/usr/bin/python
from bcc import BPF

BPF(text='int kprobe_ptrace_attach(void
*ctx) { bpf_trace_printk("ptrace_attach
called\n"); return 0; }').trace_print()
```

This program generates the following output when *ptrace_attach* is called:

```
# ./ptrace.py
derusbi-6572 [003] ....
55527.716367: 0x00000001: ptrace_attach
called
```

The quoted string assigned to the *text* variable is restricted C code. *kprobe__* is a special function prefix that creates a *kprobe* (dynamic tracing of a kernel function call) for the specified kernel function name. Our function is executed every time the *ptrace_attach* system call is used.

bpf_trace_printk can be used as a convenient hack to write to the common */sys/kernel/debug/tracing/trace_pipe* for debugging purposes, but shouldn't be used otherwise because *trace_pipe* is globally shared. The exact output of *bpf_trace_printk* depends on the options set in

/sys/kernel/debug/tracing/trace_options (see /sys/kernel/debug/tracing/README for more information). In this case, derusbi is the name and 6572 the PID of the current task. [003] is the cpu number the current task is running on, followed by IRQ-Options, a timestamp in nanoseconds, a fake value used by BPF for the instruction pointer register and our formatted message.

We can attach multiple kprobes to a function using `attach_kprobe` in python. Also, using `trace_fields()` [3] instead of `trace_print()` gives us more control over the values printed.

```
from bcc import BPF

# define BPF program
bpf_program = """
int p_event(void *ctx) {
    bpf_trace_printk("traced very meaningful
event!\n");
    return 0;
}
"""

# load BPF program
b = BPF(text=bpf_program)

#attach kprobes for sys_clone and execve
b.attach_kprobe(event=b.get_syscall_fname("c
lone"), fn_name="p_event")
b.attach_kprobe(event=b.get_syscall_fname("e
xecve"), fn_name="p_event")

while True:
    try:
        (task, pid, cpu, flags, ts, msg) =
b.trace_fields()
    except ValueError:
        continue
    print("%f\t%d\t%s\t%s" % (ts, pid, task,
msg))
```

This next example uses the `BPF_PERF_OUTPUT()` interface. This is the preferred method of pushing per-event data to user space.

```
#!/usr/bin/python

#Adapted example from
https://github.com/iovisor/bcc/blob/master/do
cs/reference_guide.md
#as well as
https://github.com/iovisor/bcc/blob/master/do
cs/tutorial_bcc_python_developer.md

from bcc import BPF

# define BPF program
bpf_program = """
#include <linux/sched.h>

struct omg_data {
    u64 gid_pid;
    u32 pid;
    u32 gid;
    u64 ts; //timestamp with nanosecond
precision
    char procname[TASK_COMM_LEN]; //holds the
name of the current process
};

BPF_PERF_OUTPUT(custom_event);

int get_thi_dete(struct pt_regs *ctx) {
    struct omg_data mdata;
```

```
        mdata.gid_pid =
bpf_get_current_pid_tgid();
        mdata.pid = (u32) mdata.gid_pid;
        mdata.gid = mdata.gid_pid >> 32;

        mdata.ts = bpf_ktime_get_ns(); //gets
timestamp in nanoseconds

        bpf_get_current_comm(&mdata.procname,
sizeof(mdata.procname));

        custom_event.perf_submit(ctx, &mdata,
sizeof(mdata));

    return 0;
}
"""

# load BPF program
b = BPF(text=bpf_program)
b.attach_kprobe(event=b.get_syscall_fname("c
lone"), fn_name="get_thi_dete")

# header
print("%-18s %-6s %-6s %-16s %s" %
("TIME(s)", "PID", "TID", "TASK", "MESSAGE"))

# process event
start = 0
def print_event(cpu, omsg_data, size):
    global start
    event = b["custom_event"].event(omsg_data)
    if start == 0:
        start = event.ts
        time_s = (float(event.ts - start)) /
1000000000
        print("%-18.9f %-6d %-6d %-16s %s" %
(time_s, event.gid, event.pid,
event.procname, "Traced sys_clone!"))

# loop with callback to print_event
b["custom_event"].open_perf_buffer(print_even
t)
while 1:
    b.perf_buffer_poll()
```

Because we don't use `bpf_trace_printk()` here, we also don't get the prepackaged information it provides. This means we need to gather event data ourselves. We use the `omg_data` struct to pass data from kernel to user space. `BPF_PERF_OUTPUT('custom_event')` creates a BPF table `custom_event` for pushing out custom event data to user space via the perf ring buffer. From `bpf.h`:

```
* u64 bpf_get_current_pid_tgid(void)
* Return
* A 64-bit integer containing the
current tgid and pid, and
* created as such:
* *current_task*\ **->tgid << 32 \|\**
* *current_task*\ **->pid**.
```

Thus, to get the thread group ID we and the PID we just shift the returned value appropriately.

To get the name of the current task we call `bpf_get_current_comm()`. From `bpf.h`:

```
* int bpf_get_current_comm(char *buf, u32
size_of_buf)
* Description
* Copy the **comm** attribute of the
current task into *buf* of
* *size_of_buf*. The **comm** attribute
contains the name of
* the executable (excluding the path)
```

```
for the current task. The
*   *size_of_buf* must be strictly
positive. On success, the
*   helper makes sure that the *buf* is
NUL-terminated. On failure,
*   it is filled with zeroes.
```

`perf_submit` submits the event for user space via a `perf` ring buffer. `print_event` is the Python function which will handle reading events from the `custom_event` stream. `b.perf_buffer_poll()` waits for events. This call is blocking.

4. Conclusion

The new additions to BPF allow for compact, powerful and performant tracing programs. Now it's just a matter of finding suitable use-cases to harness its power. Despite touching on sensitive areas of the system, the risk associated with impacting other areas of the system is reduced, thanks to being run in a sandboxed environment and static code analysis by the kernel.

5. External Links

- [1] <https://github.com/iovisor/bcc>
- [2] <https://attack.mitre.org/techniques/T1055/>
- [3] https://github.com/iovisor/bcc/blob/master/docs/reference_guide.md#2-trace_fields